

EFFECT OF SPECIMEN HISTORY ON MEASURED IN-PLANE PERMEABILITY OF FABRICS

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1 Introduction

In Liquid Composites Moulding (LCM) processes, the impregnation of textile reinforcements with liquid resin systems is frequently described by the model of a viscous liquid flowing through a porous medium, characterised by its porosity and permeability. Determination of the textile permeability is a prerequisite for optimisation of the process parameters for production of composite components applying LCM-technology, in particular location of injection gates and vents in the mould to achieve complete impregnation of the reinforcement, and for prediction of the mould fill time.

A recent international benchmark exercise [1], which gave an overview of methods for permeability measurement in practical use and the range of results obtained implementing these methods, indicated that measured in-plane permeability values for woven reinforcement fabrics can show a scatter of one order of magnitude at any given fibre volume fraction. The ratio of the principal permeability values can vary by factors of up to 2. This variability makes resin flow during reinforcement impregnation hard to predict, and uncontrollable flow may eventually result in defect formation.

While the tested fabric specimens had identical nominal properties, it was suspected that, in addition to potential error sources related to measurement set-up and execution of experiments, the observed variability can be explained by the different history of different material batches and its influence on the fabric structure. It can be speculated that variations in the structure of tested fabrics may be operator-induced during specimen preparation (cutting, stacking) or result from effects of gravity and handling during storage and transport.

Since shear, the mechanics of which was discussed in detail by Behre [2] and Skelton [3], is the main deformation mechanism of woven fabrics [4], the effect of specimen history on the fabric structure can be represented by repeated defined shear deformation. While the permeability of woven fabrics sheared to given fibre angles was studied before, e.g. by Hammami et al. [5], Smith et al. [6], Lai and Young [7] and Bickerton et al. [8], this study aims at characterising the residual effect of specimen shear history on the fabric structure (illustrated schematically in Fig. 1, and sometimes referred to as “mechanical fabric conditioning” [9]) and describing how the potential change in inter-yarn gap width in a single fabric layer with unconstrained thickness transfers into a change in permeability in a multi-layer lay-up at given levels of through-thickness compaction.

2 Fabric Geometry Analysis

2.1 Method

To simulate the effect of the material history for different fabrics, single-layer fabric specimens with unconstrained thickness were sheared to given angles and sheared back to a 0°/90° configuration. A shear frame was used, where rectangular specimens with dimensions 500 mm × 280 mm were clamped along the edges parallel to either the fabric warp or weft direction. Analysis of photographs of the fabric surface, acquired after completion of each shear cycle (i.e. sheared back to a 0°/90° configuration), allowed yarn spacing, s_y , and yarn width, w_y , to be measured in 2D projection. The width of inter-yarn gaps, w_g , can then be identified as the difference of s_y and w_y . Potential changes in yarn thickness related to changes in yarn width were not quantified here.

Starting from the initial unsheared configuration, the shear angle was increased in steps of 5° . The specimens were sheared alternately in both possible directions, indicated as “+” and “-”. For example, a specimen characterised by a shear history with a maximum shear angle of $+10^\circ$ would have undergone shear to the following angles: 0° , $+5^\circ$, -5° , $+10^\circ$.

2.2 Results

For specimens of two 2×2 twill weave carbon fibre fabrics (nominal superficial densities $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$ and $S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$, Fig. 2), yarn widths, w_y , measured for unsheared specimens and a maximum shear angle of -40° are listed in Table 1. Average inter-yarn gap widths, w_g , after undergoing different shear operations are plotted in Figs. 3 and 4.

For interpretation of the results, several caveats are to be considered. Although, for each fabric, all specimens are from the same batch (same roll) of material, every “unsheared” specimen has undergone its own specific history before the experiment, which may result in different initial configurations. The effect of shear on the fabric structure may vary depending on the alignment of the fabric specimens in the shear frame, which may not be perfect, and there may be some slack in the fabric affecting tension in the yarns when sheared. In addition, the accuracy of shear angle adjustment is limited. Finally, evaluation of images of the specimen surface may introduce uncertainty. Blurred images explain the outliers in Fig. 4.

Despite these uncertainties, the following trends can be derived from the acquired data. Figure 3 indicates that, prior to any shear operation, no gaps exist between parallel fibre bundles in the fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$, and there is no significant difference in widths of warp- and weft-yarns (Table 1). After undergoing shear operations, there are only small changes in yarn width for small maximum angles in the shear history. For maximum angles in the shear history greater than approximately 20° , which coincides with the observed onset of wrinkling in the fabric, the increase in gap width (i.e. decrease in yarn width) becomes stronger. This trend is stronger when the fabric is clamped along the warp direction than when clamped along the weft direction. In this case, the weft-yarns seem to get slightly wider at small maximum angles resulting in a negative gap

width, which means partial overlap of adjacent bundles (Note: the yarn width is measured at approximately the widest point). The difference between the initial and final yarn width (maximum shear angle -40°) is approximately identical in both fabric directions.

In the fabric with $S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$ (Fig. 4), gaps exist between parallel fibre bundles prior to any shear operation. These initial gaps are significantly wider between weft-yarns than between warp-yarns, which is related to a significant difference in yarn width (warp-yarns are wider than weft-yarns) as indicated in Table 1. After undergoing shear operations, the gap widths increase approximately linearly with increasing maximum angle in shear history (i.e. the yarn widths decrease). There appears to be a trend for the gap widths to increase more strongly when the fabric is clamped along the weft-direction than when clamped along the warp-direction, which may be related to different yarn mobility in the different fabric directions. Since this trend is weak, it will be ignored here. The increase in gap width is more significant between warp-yarns than between weft-yarns, i.e. the reduction in yarn width is stronger for warp-yarns, which are initially wider than weft-yarns.

3 Shear Resistance Measurement

3.1 Method

To understand the fabric mechanics leading to the observed changes in the fabric structure, picture frame shear tests [4] were carried out on an Instron 5969 testing machine. A 5 kN load cell was used. The cross-head speed was set to 20 mm/min. Deviating from the normal procedure for picture frame shear tests, rectangular fabric specimens were clamped along either the fabric warp or weft direction to be consistent with the procedure in Section 2. Here, the dimensions of the specimens were $200 \text{ mm} \times 100 \text{ mm}$. The difference in specimen area compared to Section 2 affects the absolute values of shear resistance, but not the fabric behaviour at different shear angles. Conversion of the cross-head displacement on the testing machine to fabric shear angles allowed the same shear cycles as in Section 2 to be reproduced.

3.2 Results

For the fabrics in Fig. 2, shear angle and shear force were calculated from the recorded cross-head displacement and the force applied to the picture frame [4]. Typical results for all shear cycles are plotted in Fig. 5 (for clarity, only the loading phase of each shear cycle is plotted, the unloading phase is omitted). For evaluation of the data, the same caveats as in Section 2 apply. Of particular concern is the accuracy of specimen alignment in the picture frame. Even slight misalignment may result in asymmetry of the curves (in Fig. 5, for $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$) due to an offset in shear angle and tension induced in the fibres.

For the fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$, detailed analysis of the data plotted in Fig. 5 suggest that, for shear cycles with maximum shear angles of up to approximately 20° , the shear force as a function of the shear angle follows approximately the same trace in each cycle. If the maximum angle is greater than approximately 20° , the absolute value of the shear force in each cycle is smaller than in previous cycles (in the range of shear angles smaller than the maximum angles in previous cycles). Increasingly more additional force is required in the range of shear angles greater than the maximum angles in previous cycles.

For the fabric with $S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$, the absolute value of the shear force in each cycle is smaller than in previous cycles. The difference appears to increase with increasing maximum shear angle. The additional force required in the range of shear angles greater than the maximum angles in previous cycles appears to drop off with increasing maximum angle.

4 In-Plane Permeability Measurement

4.1 Method

For the 2×2 twill weave carbon fibre fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$, the in-plane permeability was characterised experimentally in unsaturated flow experiments (with radial injection geometry) at constant injection pressure. Synthetic oil with given viscosity-temperature characteristics was used as a test fluid.

At a cavity height of 2 mm, specimens consisted of 3 fabric layers, corresponding to a fibre volume fraction $V_f = 0.56$. All layers had the same orientation. Specimens were prepared by shearing

each fabric layer individually following the procedure described in Section 2.1. Shear angles were increased in steps of 5° (alternating in “+” and “-” direction) until the target maximum angle was reached. Areas which may have been damaged by clamping of the fabric in the shear frame were cut off from the originally rectangular layers. Square specimens with dimensions $280 \text{ mm} \times 280 \text{ mm}$ were used for the injection experiments.

For the fabric with $S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$, the permeability was measured in a previous series of experiments [10] for 9 layers at a cavity height of 3.5 mm, corresponding to $V_f = 0.40$. So far, the permeability was only determined for unsheared specimens.

4.2 Results

For the fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$, results for the measured in-plane permeability of specimens with different history are listed in Table 2. For both clamping configurations, the principal in-plane permeability values, K_1 and K_2 , increase approximately linearly with increasing maximum shear angle. The increase tends to be slightly stronger for specimens clamped along the warp direction than for those clamped along the weft direction. There is no clear trend for the ratio K_1/K_2 to change. The ratio of the semi-major and semi-minor axes of the flow front ellipse in radial flow, R_1/R_2 , which is equal to the square root of the ratio K_1/K_2 , is approximately constant at a value of 1.2. This implies that the flow front shape is similar to a circle, and the direction of the principal flow direction is sensitive to small changes in fabric structure. This is reflected in the observed changes in the angle θ .

For the fabric with $S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$, the measured permeability is given in Table 3. Here, the orientation of the principal flow direction coincides with the weft-direction, because the gap width between weft-yarns tends to be significantly higher than the gap width between warp-yarns (Fig. 4).

5 In-Plane Resin Flow Simulation

5.1 Method

Based on the data in Table 1, Fig. 3, and additional 3D geometry data for unsheared specimens acquired using micro-Computed Tomography (μ -CT), geometrical models of 3 layers of the fabric with S_0

= 660 g/m² at a cavity height of 2 mm (corresponding to the experiments described in Section 4) were generated using the software TexGen [11]. The dimensions of the models were chosen such that at least one complete fabric unit cell (4 × 4 yarns) was included in each layer. For relative positioning of the layers, two cases, zero nesting and random nesting, were considered.

In a first step, the geometrical model of the unsheared fabric was generated. To avoid yarn intersections at cross-over points, realistic yarn paths were defined and yarn cross-sectional geometries were adapted locally. Then, observed changes in yarn widths due to the fabric shear history were introduced successively by manual adjustment of the model geometries. The simplifying assumption was made that the yarn width in a lay-up at given level of compaction is the same as the width in a single fabric layer with unconstrained thickness, i.e. potential flattening and widening of the yarns due to through-thickness compression was ignored here (Fig. 6).

The geometrical models were used to generate flow domains for Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations containing yarns and the surrounding empty spaces in the tool cavity. The flow domains were meshed with uniform hexahedral (brick shaped) voxels with appropriate size for representation of geometrical detail. The permeabilities of yarns, which can be estimated based on the models proposed by Gebart [12], are typically small compared to the overall permeabilities of the fabric stacks. Thus, the yarns can be assumed to be impermeable in order to reduce the computational cost for CFD simulations. Steady-state flow through the pore spaces was simulated using the commercial CFD code Ansys CFXTM. Translational periodic boundary conditions were set on opposite faces of the textile unit cell domain in weft and warp direction to represent a continuous reinforcement. A flow-driving pressure drop was applied in either warp or weft direction. Non-slip wall boundary conditions were specified at the top and bottom faces of the domain to simulate flow along the mould surfaces during in-plane fabric impregnation. From the applied pressure gradients along different fabric directions and the calculated average flow velocities, in-plane permeabilities were determined. In a first step, the mesh sensitivity of the predicted permeabilities was assessed. Based on the

results, the number of voxels for the entire flow domain was chosen as 150 × 150 × 90 (warp × weft × thickness) to obtain a reasonable balance between computation time and accuracy for all following simulations.

The same procedure was applied to modelling flow through 9 layers of the fabric with $S_0 = 285$ g/m² at a cavity height of 3.5 mm. A mesh with 150 × 150 × 270 hexahedral voxels was used for the flow simulations, for which convergence of the results was found. As for the other fabric, cases with zero nesting and random nesting were simulated.

5.2 Results

Examples for geometrical models of unsheared fabric ($S_0 = 660$ g/m²) with zero nesting and random nesting are shown in Fig. 7. In the models, weft-yarns are oriented along the x -direction, warp-yarns are oriented along the y -direction.

Results for the permeabilities in both fabric directions, derived from the results of CFD simulations, are listed in Table 4. The data indicate that, in addition to the effect of nesting, which was discussed by Hoes et al. [13], the fabric history has a significant effect on the permeability. Calculated permeabilities are higher for random nesting than for zero nesting, reflecting different geometries of flow channels forming in the lay-up. The permeability in weft direction, K_x , is consistently higher than the permeability in warp direction, K_y . The ratio K_x/K_y tends to be higher for zero nesting than for random nesting. With increasing maximum angle in the shear history, K_x and K_y increase since the inter-yarn gap width increases as illustrated in Fig. 3.

For the fabric with $S_0 = 285$ g/m², permeabilities in both fabric directions, derived from the CFD simulations, are listed in Table 5. Due to lack of experimental data for comparison, only results for the unsheared fabric and a shear history with a maximum shear angle of -40° are listed here. After undergoing the shear operations, the permeability in both fabric directions is higher than for the unsheared fabric, since the inter-yarn gap widths increase as illustrated in Fig. 4. The permeability in weft direction is consistently higher than the permeability in warp direction. The ratio of permeability values in the different fabric directions tends to be higher for zero nesting than for random nesting. It is smaller for the fabric that has

undergone the shear operations than for the unsheared fabric.

6 Discussion

For the fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$, parallel yarns are in contact with each other if previously unsheared (Fig. 2), suggesting that lateral yarn compression is the main deformation mechanism in fabric shear. The average yarn width in the fabric decreases with increasing maximum angle in the shear history, and the gap width increases accordingly. The residual effect of shear on the gap width is small for small maximum shear angles, more significant for shear angles greater than the angle for onset of fabric wrinkling at approximately 20° (Fig 3).

These geometrical observations correlate well with the measured shear resistance data (Fig. 5), which suggest that lateral yarn compression is almost “elastic” for shear angles up to approximately 20° and relatively small shear forces. For greater shear angles, reduced force in each shear cycle compared to the previous one (in the range of angles reached in previous cycles) suggests that, in each cycle, the fabric loses part of its shear resistance due to “plastic” yarn deformation. With increasing shear angle (beyond angles reached in previous cycles), increasingly more force is required due to stiffening of the yarns in lateral compression with increasing density of filament packing (and increasing yarn thickness) at reduced yarn width.

For the fabric with $S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$, geometrical considerations, based on values for w_y and s_y determined in Section 2, indicate that, independent of the clamping configuration, adjacent weft yarns are in contact if the shear angle is greater than approximately 34° , adjacent warp yarns are in contact if the shear angle is greater than approximately 25° . While there is no lateral yarn compression for shear angles smaller than 25° , the observed linear reduction in yarn width with increasing maximum shear angle (Fig. 4) is related to friction in yarn cross-over points and constraints on rotational yarn movement imposed by crimp as discussed by Nguyen et al. [14].

The linear reduction in yarn width correlates with the measured shear resistance data (Fig. 5), which indicate that the absolute value of the shear force in each cycle is smaller than in previous cycles. This suggests that, in each shear cycle, the fabric loses

part of its shear resistance due to “plastic” yarn deformation. The additional force required for fabric shear in the range of angles greater than the maximum angles in previous shear cycles appears to drop off with increasing maximum angle, suggesting that, in the range of angles discussed here, reduction of the yarn width is not sufficient to result in stiffening in lateral compression.

This difference in behaviour compared to the fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$ is related to the yarn cross-sectional shape and filament count. As illustrated in Fig. 2 and Table 1, yarn widths in both fabrics are similar. However, in the fabric with higher S_0 and $c_f = 12\text{K}$, the yarns have greater thickness due to constraints on the maximum yarn width. This lateral pre-compression is thought to result in higher resistance to permanent filament reordering in the yarns. On the other hand, in the fabric with lower S_0 and $c_f = 6\text{K}$, yarns are flatter and, due to lack of constraints on the cross-sectional dimensions, are thought to be more susceptible to filament reordering. Hence, the yarns deform more easily in fabric shear.

For the fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$, a shear history with a maximum angle of -40° resulted in a reduction in yarn width by 9 % or 10 % (Table 1) and the corresponding opening up of inter-yarn gaps. For the same shear history, an increase in permeabilities by a factor of approximately 1.8 (clamped along warp) or 1.7 (clamped along weft) was observed experimentally. This indicates a correlation between changes in the fabric structure and measured permeability values at different shear histories.

Measured (Table 2) and predicted (Table 4) permeability values are compared in Fig. 8, where K_x is assumed to correspond to K_1 , K_y to K_2 . This ignores changes in the orientation of the principal flow directions, which is sensitive to small changes in the fabric structure since the fabric properties are similar in both fabric directions. For the unsheared fabric and the fabric with a shear history with a maximum angle of -20° , predicted permeability values are similar to measured values. A further increase in the maximum angle in shear history results in an increasing difference between measured and predicted permeabilities, where the predictions overestimate the experimental data by significant margins. This difference suggests that the reduction

in yarn width (and potential increase in yarn thickness) caused by shear in fabric layers with unconstrained thickness is partially reversed by yarn flattening and widening in through-thickness compression of fabric layers when stacked in the cavity during fluid injection, which is not considered in the computational model (Fig. 6). However, the increase in inter-yarn gap width induced in the uncompressed fabric layers is at least partially conserved. The accuracy of simulation-based permeability predictions for specimens with large maximum angles in the shear histories is expected to improve when the simplified geometrical yarn models in Fig. 6 are updated with more accurate 3D data, which can be acquired employing μ -CT to allow the effect of yarn flattening and widening for compressed stacks of fabric layers to be quantified. For the fabric with $S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$, the accuracy of permeability predictions based on flow simulations for the unsheared fabric improved compared to previous simulations [10], because more accurate geometry data were available. A shear history with a maximum angle of -40° resulted in an increase in inter-yarn gap width in the order of 80 % (between warp-yarns) and 30 % (between weft-yarns), respectively. This significant increase in gap width in a single layer transferred into an increase in predicted permeability of a fabric lay-up. After undergoing the shear operations, the permeability is less anisotropic than in the unsheared fabric, because the difference in gap widths in both fabric directions is reduced (Fig. 4). However, the predicted change in permeability caused by the shear history is significantly smaller than for the fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$, because the relative change in inter-yarn gap widths is smaller (Figs. 3 and 4). As for the other fabric, yarn flattening and widening in

through-thickness compression is expected to reverse partially the increase in permeability caused by the fabric shear history. More experimental and numerical data will be generated for this fabric to complete this study.

7 Conclusions

For two different 2×2 twill weave carbon fibre fabrics, the effect of specimen history was simulated by repeated defined shear deformation. For single layers with unconstrained thickness, quantitative evaluation of photographic image data of the fabric surface in $0^\circ/90^\circ$ configuration indicated that the inter-yarn gap width increases with increasing maximum angle in the specimen shear history.

Picture frame shear tests indicated different shear behaviour for different fabrics, which have different dominating yarn deformation mechanisms. This is related to different dependencies of the residual inter-yarn gap width on the shear history.

Experimentally determined permeability values for multi-layer fabric stacks at given levels of through-thickness compaction increased with increasing maximum angle in the specimen shear history. For the example discussed here, an increase in permeability by up to 80 % was observed.

CFD analyses of resin flow were found to predict experimental permeability data with reasonable accuracy if accurate geometry data are available. Comparison of predicted and measured permeability data for different fabric shear history implied that through-thickness compression of the fabric in the cavity partially reverses the increase in inter-yarn gap width induced in the uncompressed fabric layers.

Fig. 1. Residual effect of specimen shear history on fabric structure.

Fig. 2. Surfaces of two different 2×2 twill weave fabrics, both unsheared; left: superficial density $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$, yarn filament count $c_f = 12\text{K}$; right: $S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$, $c_f = 6\text{K}$.

Table 1. Width of yarns, w_y , for specimens of two different 2×2 twill weave fabrics, unsheared and after undergoing shear to a maximum angle of -40° , characterised by the superficial densities, S_0 ; relative changes in yarn width, $\Delta w_y/w_y$, are also given.

fabric $S_0 / \text{g/m}^2$	clamped along	w_y / mm (warp)			$\Delta w_y / w_y$	w_y / mm (weft)		$\Delta w_y / w_y$
		unsheared	max. -40°			unsheared	max. -40°	
660	warp	2.534 ± 0.079	2.309 ± 0.070	-9 %	2.501 ± 0.065	2.262 ± 0.065	-10 %	
	weft	2.595 ± 0.096	2.344 ± 0.076	-10 %	2.459 ± 0.098	2.242 ± 0.115	-9 %	
285	warp	2.640 ± 0.147	2.403 ± 0.173	-9 %	2.412 ± 0.188	2.268 ± 0.255	-6 %	
	weft	2.620 ± 0.156	2.415 ± 0.106	-8 %	2.433 ± 0.237	2.306 ± 0.168	-5 %	

Fig. 3. Average width of inter-yarn gaps, w_g , for a specimen of a 2×2 twill weave fabric ($S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$) after undergoing different shear operations; diamond symbols: gap width between warp-yarns; square symbols: gap width between weft-yarns.

Fig. 4. Average width of inter-yarn gaps, w_g , for a specimen of a 2×2 twill weave fabric ($S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$) after undergoing different shear operations; diamond symbols: gap width between warp-yarns; square symbols: gap width between weft-yarns.

Fig. 5. Typical results of picture frame shear tests: shear force as a function of the shear angle for all shear cycles; for clarity, only the loading phase of each shear cycle is plotted; both data sets were measured for specimens clamped along the fabric warp direction.

Table 2. Measured principal permeability values, K_1 and K_2 , angle θ indicating the orientation of K_1 relative to the fabric weft direction, and ratio, K_1/K_2 , for a 2x2 twill weave fabric ($S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$) at a given fibre volume fraction, $V_f = 0.56$.

history	$K_1 / 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$	$K_2 / 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$	θ	K_1 / K_2
unsheared	0.513 ± 0.102 ($\pm 20 \%$)	0.354 ± 0.070 ($\pm 20 \%$)	$-39^\circ \pm 15^\circ$	1.457 ± 0.179 ($\pm 12 \%$)
sheared, clamped weft, max. -20°	0.732 ± 0.198 ($\pm 27 \%$)	0.490 ± 0.050 ($\pm 10 \%$)	$-32^\circ \pm 30^\circ$	1.535 ± 0.596 ($\pm 39 \%$)
sheared, clamped weft, max. -40°	0.864 ± 0.041 ($\pm 5 \%$)	0.589 ± 0.016 ($\pm 3 \%$)	$85^\circ \pm 29^\circ$	1.468 ± 0.098 ($\pm 7 \%$)
sheared, clamped warp, max. $+10^\circ$	0.693 ± 0.239 ($\pm 34 \%$)	0.387 ± 0.073 ($\pm 19 \%$)	$109^\circ \pm 23^\circ$	1.756 ± 0.362 ($\pm 21 \%$)
sheared, clamped warp, max. -40°	0.947 ± 0.208 ($\pm 22 \%$)	0.652 ± 0.038 ($\pm 6 \%$)	$118^\circ \pm 17^\circ$	1.444 ± 0.234 ($\pm 16 \%$)

Table 3. Measured principal permeability values, K_1 and K_2 , angle θ indicating the orientation of K_1 relative to the fabric weft direction, and ratio, K_1/K_2 , for a 2x2 twill weave fabric ($S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$) at a given fibre volume fraction, $V_f = 0.40$.

history	$K_1 / 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$	$K_2 / 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$	θ	K_1 / K_2
unsheared	3.645 ± 0.438 ($\pm 12 \%$)	2.237 ± 0.248 ($\pm 11 \%$)	$1^\circ \pm 14^\circ$	1.650 ± 0.289 ($\pm 18 \%$)

Fig. 6. Typical cross-sections of yarns in a 2x2 twill weave fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$ in geometrical models for resin flow simulations; Δx , Δy and Δz are co-ordinates relative to the centroid of the cross-sections; top: weft-yarn; bottom: warp-yarn.

Fig. 7. Geometrical models of unsheared lay-up for 2×2 twill weave fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$ (3 layers, 2 mm total thickness); top: zero nesting; bottom: random nesting.

Table 4. Predicted permeability values, K_x and K_y , corresponding to the directions indicated in Fig. 7, and ratio K_x/K_y , for specimens of 2×2 twill weave fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$ with different shear history and different nesting configuration; fibre volume fraction $V_f = 0.56$.

history	nesting	$K_y / 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$	$K_x / 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$	K_x / K_y
unsheared	zero	0.405	0.530	1.309
	random	0.550	0.670	1.218
sheared, clamped weft, max. -20°	zero	0.419	0.600	1.432
	random	0.639	0.846	1.324
sheared, clamped weft, max. -30°	zero	0.504	0.860	1.706
	random	0.742	1.060	1.429
sheared, clamped weft, max. -40°	zero	1.050	1.640	1.562
	random	1.490	1.880	1.262

Fig. 8. Comparison of measured and predicted permeability values, K_1 and K_2 , for a 2×2 twill weave fabric with $S_0 = 660 \text{ g/m}^2$, fibre volume fraction $V_f = 0.56$; diamond symbols: simulation, zero nesting; square symbols: simulation, random nesting; triangular symbols: experiment.

Table 5. Predicted permeability values, K_{warp} and K_{weft} , and ratio K_{weft}/K_{warp} , for specimens of 2×2 twill weave fabric with $S_0 = 285 \text{ g/m}^2$ with different shear history and different nesting configuration; fibre volume fraction $V_f = 0.40$.

history	nesting	$K_{warp} / 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$	$K_{weft} / 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$	K_{weft} / K_{warp}
unsheared	zero	2.20	4.08	1.86
	random	2.38	3.37	1.41
sheared, clamped warp, max. -40°	zero	3.69	5.33	1.44
	random	4.34	5.07	1.17

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